

Representation of India in the Inheritance of Loss by Kiran Desai

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Abstract:

Like her mother Anita Desai, Kiran Desai emerges as a gifted writer. She is the winner of Man Booker Prize, 2006. Kiran Desai is deeply interested in India. The present paper endeavours to bring forth the various aspects of India and its people. Entire novel is set in the backdrop of insurgency rising in the North-East. The novel opens and ends with insurgency. She openly talks about GNLNF movement, Indian culture, Multiculturalism, Immigration, topographical description of nature through the characters of the novel. This novel is essentially a study of losses- loss of culture, loss of identity, loss of human relations, loss of emotional binding, loss of human values etc. Kiran Desai makes the novel Indian - both by contents and form. She uses a number of slangs, dialectic words, abuses of various regions, vulgar and obscene expressions. "The Inheritance of loss" was the result of eight years' of work, writing of broken people, difficult lives; writing not just about India but about the Indian communities in the world.

Keywords: Insurgency, losses, Immigration, slangs, Indian People.

Introduction:

Kiran Desai, winner of the prestigious Man Booker Prize, 2006 for her second novel "The Inheritance of Loss" and daughter of the illustrious novelist of Indian Diaspora Anita Desai, was born in Chandigarh, on September 3, 1971. Kiran Desai is deeply interested in India - the India of 1980s - honestly represents the mixed image of India. The present paper endeavours to bring forth the various aspects of India and its people. Desai observes everything through the "lens of being Indian." During Jaipur Literature Festival, in an interview she expressed her pleasant experience: "It's best time to be an Indian writer....I do know that present day India isn't really my subject". She goes back to India of the 1980s. It is this feeling that caught between two continents that infuses the novel.

Politically, India was hit by insurgency. It imposed a big threat to law and order. Entire novel is set in the backdrop of insurgency rising in the North-East, i.e. GNLNF movement which disrupted the normal life, tourism, business and peace. Out of fifty-three chapters of the novel more than eighteen chapters are exclusively devoted to describe insurgency to highlight the dismal picture of the region. Desai curtly blames the policy makers for these violent movements occurred during that time in India. "Gorkhaland for Gorkhas" is the motto of the movement; the activists work on universal guerilla fashion. Kukri sickles, axes, kitchen knives, spade or any kind of firearm they look for to make the movement more and more violent to force the government to grant statehood. The major theme running throughout the novel, "The Inheritance of loss" is closely related to colonialism and the effects of colonialism and india was the colony of British

people. Gyan is radicalized largely because love makes him feel inadequate and fearful for his manhood. He is portrayed as immature and moody. Although Gyan and Sai fall in love, Gyan becomes caught in the Gorkha independence movement and betrays Sai by telling his fellow rebels about the judge's firearms at Cho Oyu. Gyan's involvement in the separatist movement is the reflection of young Indians' deep-rooted frustration, for which Gyan even sacrifices the love of Sai. A feeling of "martyrdom crept over him". The novel opens and ends with insurgency. In the opening chapter, Jemu's house is besieged and a hunting rifle is plundered; chapter fifty-two ends with Bijou robbed by Gurkha mercenaries and chased by dogs in the jungle.

The novel portrays the Indian society as poverty-stricken; moreover illiteracy, unemployment, xenophobia, cultural conflicts, traditional values, customs, practices; and multiplicity of languages, religions, faiths constitute the very structure of the society in which the novelist is deeply interested. Though she draws a dismal picture of the Indian society. Gyan's involvement in GNLNF movement and frustration caused by the extreme polarities he witnesses between the poor and the rich brings drastic changes in his attitude and love. The novel is the brilliant study of Indian culture---the culture in its transitional phase. Changes are brought out by "colonial neurosis," craze for the western values, manners, language and glamorous life style; impact of modernization, consumerism, globalization and deep-rooted reaction to indigenous values which failed to sustain life. Characters feel inferior, bounded and defeated by their Indian heritage confronted with colonialism.

Multiculturalism is another characteristic feature of Indian society. Jemu, Sai, Biju, cook, Lola, Noni, Booty, Potty, Gyan, Mr. and Mrs. Mistry belong to different cultural backgrounds. Desai herself inherited multiculturalism from her parents and grandparents. Her maternal grandmother was a German; grandfather was a refugee from Bangladesh. Her paternal grandparents came from Gujarat, and her grandfather was educated in England. Although she has not lived in India since she was 14, she returns to the family home in Delhi every year. She maintains a convivial attitude to all cultures and mildly exposes the vanity and hypocrisy imbibed in them. Immigration problem is one of the most striking problems. Most of the Indians and the Third World citizens face such a problem in Europe and America. Desai herself has spent more than twenty years in America. It was her own experience and innate talks with immigrants in America that she could highlight the problem so emphatically. Biju, Saeed, Harish, Saran, Jeev, Rishi and thousands of Africans, Latin Americans and Asians working in America and Europe exemplify the bitter experiences of the immigrants. Nature and Landscape description occupies a large canvas of the novel; though it extends from Manhattan to Himalayas, it is central to Piphit, Kalimpong, Cho Oyu, and Darjeeling. Topography, scenic beauty, variety of vegetation, changing colors of the sky, patches of clouds, rain, mist, mountain tops, Teesta river, thick forests, cluster of houses, vapour, ice, zig-zag roads and seasonal changes, etc. define nature in the novel. It is a sensuous beauty that delights the novelist very much, simultaneously, it is contrasted with rising insurgency and its violent outbreak disrupting normal life. Her treatment of nature is highly poetic and Wordsworthian, finding deeper import in it. The novel opens with a nature description: "All day, the colors had been those of dusk, might moving like a water creature across the great flanks of mountains possessed of ocean shadows and depths. Briefly visible above the vapour, Kanchenjunga was a far peak whittled out of ice, gathering the last of the light, a plume of snow blown high by the storms at its summit." Her involvement in nature and landscapes of India confirms her unending interest and diasporic articulation. Unlike Wordsworth, Desai hardly tries to divinize nature or feels the presence of God anywhere.

The novel is essentially a study of losses---loss of culture, loss of identity, loss of human relations, loss of emotional bindings, loss of human values, loss of rationality, loss of peace and harmony, loss of human beings' faith in each, etc. Sense of loss is an integral

part of every character's life; they are insecure, unmoored, struggling to survive in the modern world, unsure of whether they will ever see the benefits of globalization; characters unnecessarily feel inferior due to their Indian heritage. The novel explores the lives of characters who are trapped in India's class system--- both the lower class and the upper class. The characters' hopes and dreams are conveyed in the novel, along with their ultimate dream of immigrating to America and finally escaping the rigid caste system of their homeland. As far as India was concerned, the infamous Macaulay Minute of February 2, 1835, declared the superiority of colonial education over native Education. The target recipient of colonial education was the males. It aimed to create a sort of inaccurate doubling of the colonized as a reflection of the colonizers. A particular variety of British culture is projected as a tool for linguistic and cultural homogenisation and normalization in the present case. Kiran Desai in her novel, *The Inheritance of Loss* (2006) attempts to locate the blurring lines of the history of Indian mental architecture from the colonial rule to the contemporary time. Desai skillfully demonstrates this through the convergence of the tormented past and an indeterminately positioned multicultural present. All through the narrative woven with assorted and generically complex composition, Desai offers a panoramic representation of a constructed reality where individuals are engaged in an incessant search for personal identity.

Kiran Desai makes the novel Indian--- both by content and form. Whether its topography, idyllic beauty or the elaborate description of insurgency, description of mountains, mist, changing seasons, Kalimpong, Cho Oyu, Darjeeling, Piphit, Immigration problem, Culture conflicts, the inhabitants or the inner mindscapes of characters, Desai frees herself from the stereo-typed Euro-centric models and honestly and independently depicts India. Her use of language is another powerful technique to create the manifest sense of Indian-ness. She prefers American English and tries to make it Indianized. She has encountered with American and British writers of English and studied creative writing at Columbia University. Subsequently, she has experimented a lot with the language. Use of popular slangs, dialectic words, abuses of various regions, vulgar and obscene expressions introduce an element of naturalism; Indian vocabulary, Indian metaphors and imagery, etc. are highly supportive to fillip the portrayal of picture and sensibility of India. Indian vocabulary creates a congenial

atmosphere to transport the reader into that realm where India resides.

Use of popular slangs, dialectic words, abuses of various regions, vulgar and obscene expressions are frequently used: nakhra, pakora, huzoor, chhang, mia-bibi, mithai, pitaji, Angreji Khana, salwars, kamala hai, Baap re!, laddoos, dhotis, jhora, pallu, Budhoo, choksee, Neps, Namaste, aiyiye, baethiye, khaiye, dhanayawad, shukria, chapattis, jalebi, haveli, tika, chokra, murga-murgi, bania, dhobi, hubshi, haat, atta, srikhand, kundan, peepal, choolah, rasta roko, phata phat, bilkul bekar, Jai Gorkha, saag, bhai, Gora, ghas phoos, goondas, sukhtara, chooran, jamun, tatti, roti-namak, gadhas, murdabad, parathas, tamasha, chappals, desi, etc. The Inheritance of loss, was the result of eight years' of work, writing of broken people, difficult lives; writing not just about India but Indian communities in the world. It was quite difficult, emotional experience for Desai, because she was devastated and sad by the end of the book where "loss" predominates. Binnie Krisenbaum has rightly commented about the novel: "A nation's tragedy great and small are revealed through the hopes and the dreams, the innocence and the arrogance, the love betrayed and the all, too, human failings of a superbly realized cast of characters. Kiran Desai writes of Post-colonial India, of its poor as well as its privileged, with a cold eye and a warm heart." *The Inheritance of loss* is set in quite different background than that of her first book *Hullabaloo in the Guava orchard*, which is the story about a middle class post-office clerk who wants to avoid his failure and jumps on the guava tree in order to become a hermit. All the characters revolve around the guava tree. Where as *The Inheritance of loss* deals basically about the problems of migration faced by her characters, their strains and difficulties. Political, social, cultural, economical, immigration, nature and landscape, Indianized English all aspects are dealt in and described in a comprehensive manner which is not only entertaining but also highly informative.

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